

**Evolution of Digital Marketing
Marketing Research (3254)
Individual Assignment**

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Abstract

Digital marketing

By

- **Kinza Yasar, Technical Writer, 2019**
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Digital marketing is a broader factor because the present digital devices and the platforms have been developed with some of the latest technologies and this is expected to continuously by the world. Digital era started with the introduction of internet and the different digital platforms and now high technology base digital devices have been introduced to effectively manage the digital marketing factors (Kinza, 2019)

Present generation is rapidly adapting towards the digital environment as the users have identify all the prevailing opportunities with the digital devices and the digital platforms. Some of the present major companies like Google, Facebook and some other digital platforms were started with smaller steps and now these organizations are perceived as world bigger organizations with billions of revenue opportunities (Avantika, Simple learn , 2023)

Below evaluated the introduction of the digital marketing with the examples and further elaborated the present situation of the digital marketing industry with the emerging technologies

History and the debut of the digital marketing

The History and Evolution of Digital Marketing

By Avantika Monnappa

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Digital marketing word first used in the year 1990, digital era was started with the development of internet and the different web platforms. The first web platform was web 1.0 and this allowed users to find the required information, but they were not allowed to share this information over the web. In this era, most of the marketers were not sure the effectiveness of digital marketing because they had some of the uncertainties whether their strategies would work as the internet was not developed widest manner (Avantika, Digital , 2023)

In the year 1993, an organization purchased few banner ads for their activities, and this happened after the first clickable banner started live, this became the debut of the digital era towards the marketing because with these improvements different new technologies entered to the digital market place by the year 1994 and the Yahoo also was launched in this same year

Google is one of the well-developed digital platforms within the present digital marketing industry and this platform was launched in 1998 and presently holds a bigger place in the digital marketing industry. After the Google launch, there were many of the smaller search engines introduced to the industry and this became the reason towards the start of the search engine traffic and in the year 2006 search engine traffic was reported about 6.4 billion in a single month. With the development of Web 2.0, people became highly attractive towards the digital activities as the Web 2.0 provided the opportunities for the users to interact with other users and the businesses (Unesco, 2023)

After the above developments, the products and services were started to market in the different digital platforms and the people highly started to spend their time with different social media platforms such as Facebook, Twitter, Pinterest, Instagram and some other platforms

The mobile era

Mobile Marketing in The Digital Era

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- **Publisher: Sankalp Publications**

Usage of the smartphones were started by the year 2010 onwards and with this people started to manage most of their communications using the smartphones and further started internet browsing, emailing, ecommerce purchasing and many of the day-to-day activities through the smartphones and the smartphone is one of the essential objects need to have by the people. At present 65% of people spent their time with digital platforms through the smartphones and the present digital advertising industry value is perceived around \$200 billion including social media advertising, Google advertising and some other different platforms as well

Growth of digital marketing industry

Digital marketing industry started it is rapid growth with the development of internet and smart devices and present all these digital platforms are well developed with the latest technologies like artificial intelligent and with these people and the organizations are executive their many of the tasks highly effective and convenient manner. As a result of growth of digital marketing 5 Ds of digital marketing, PESO model and some other new developments came to the world and with these developments digital marketing industry started to reach towards the highest levels as these developments have introduced different new strategies for the digital marketing activities to communicate the products and services highly successful manner (Jack, 2023)

THE EVOLUTION OF DIGITAL MARKETING

John Hughes August 31, 2020

Development of Digital devices

these are the tangible digital devices people are being used to implement the various types of digital marketing activities. These devices are smartphones, laptops, computers, smart tables, smart watches and many other. These devices are being updated with the emerging technologies and now people got the opportunities to fulfill their needs and wants highly convenient manner (5Ds, 2023)

Digital content platforms – Well effective digital content platforms have been introduced for the users to interact with these, as a result, advertisers can effectively communicate for the market to gain more business opportunities

Growth of Digital media

There are two main digital media platforms have been introduced such as the paid and owned media platforms, under each platform there are various types of digital tools available and these digital media platforms are highly effective to sponsor for the paid ads to reach for the required target audiences

Paid media digital tools are social media platforms, Google, different websites and others. With the social media platforms possible to sponsor for the posts, stories, content videos, bumper ads and many other strategies to reach for the customers and these platforms effectiveness is continuously growing as these platforms are updated with the emerging technologies. When the users are interacting with these platforms that they can comment their opinions, share the posts, react with emojis and many other ways, based on that, users can clearly identify the quality of the products and services. Social media platforms have developed their technology facilitating for the organizations to communicate their products and services targeting for the required target audience based on the demographic and geographic factors, Google also highly effective for the Google ads, SEO/SEM strategies, website ads and many other ways to reach for the customers through the digital advertisements.

Growth of Digital data

Digital platforms have developed different analytical tools for the identification about the target audience, digital data and many of the details related to the digital marketing campaigns, these tools provide the knowledge regarding the web traffic, reach percentage of the ads, user interaction rate, conversion rate and many other insights to determine the quality of the campaigns

Growth of Digital technology

Digital technology is one of the important area within the present digital marketing industry because the technology is rapidly growing and as a result artificial intelligent solutions has developed, blockchain technology, data monetization, Omni channel and many of the technological developments have been introduced for the digital marketing industry to get the maximum opportunities towards the customers

Digital marketing during the Covid

Covid season was the booming stage for digital marketing because some of the digital platforms got the opportunities to increase the users and customers during this season with the implementation of the work from home concept. Many of the ecommerce platforms got massive opportunities to increase their revenue and promote their business highly with the start of online purchasing and the online banking applications got more users and the society highly started to do their banking activities from home without travelling towards the physical branches. Covid became another positive milestone towards the digital marketing, and this shows digital marketing is a continues developing thing within the present marketplace

Digital marketing at the moment

Organizations are rapidly moving towards the various types of digital solutions because the present market trend is high for various types of digital things because the social environment is highly using different types of digital devices and spending their time with the different digital platforms, and this has become the main reason towards the development of digital marketing rather than the traditional offline marketing activities. Digital marketing has many of the opportunities because the millions of people have engaged with many of the digital platforms and with this possible to reach towards the required customer audience based on the demographic and geographic factors. Social media marketing is highly growing because the social media platforms have provided many of the strategies to implement the different communication activities such as the content marketing, sponsored posts, stories, videos, bumper ads and other. When comparing the investments on the digital marketing that has a clear difference with the offline marketing campaigns because the digital marketing campaign cost is highly low and having the opportunities to select the required packages based on the buying powers of the people

ZMOT

With the growth of digital marketing, ZMOT started, ZMOT is regarding the purchasing steps of the people and with the impacts of the digital marketing people buying journey steps have reduced because in earlier people happened to visit for the physical market for products and services evaluation and for the negotiation as well, with the digital marketing people got the opportunities to do all the evaluations through the available digital platforms and then visit for the market place for the actual purchase. With the development of the ecommerce people got the capabilities to do their purchasing activities from home as the products are delivered towards the doorstep (Jagoda, 2023)

Conclusion

Above elaborated the history of the digital marketing industry including the initial stage of the digital environment, digital factors had been developed with the introduction of the internet and the digital devices and these have been further developed with the emerging technologies and now the world has highly digitalized showing this present world situation as digital era. With these development, digital marketing industry is in a top level within the present business environment as the digital platforms are highly effective to for the communication activities

References

- 5Ds. (2023, December 5). Retrieved from 5Ds: <https://goadfuel.com/5-ds-of-digital-marketing>
- Avantika. (2023, December 5). *Digital* . Retrieved from Digi: <https://www.simplilearn.com/history-and-evolution-of-digital-marketing-article>
- Avantika. (2023, November 7). *Simple learn* . Retrieved from Simple learn : <https://www.simplilearn.com/history-and-evolution-of-digital-marketing-article#:~:text=the%20most%20ground.-,History%20of%20Digital%20Marketing,this%20information%20over%20the%20web>
- Jack. (2023, December 21). *Digi*. Retrieved from digi: <https://www.google.com/url?sa=t&rct=j&q=&esrc=s&source=web&cd=&ved=2ahUKEwiq6peZzuKDAxVRTGwGHUGBD40QFnoECCQQA&url=https%3A%2F%2Fthesocialshepherd.com%2Fblog%2Fdigital-marketing-statistics%23%3A~%3Atext%3DDigital%2520Marketing%2520is%2520One%2520of%2520th>
- Jagoda. (2023, May 5). *ZMOT*. Retrieved from ZMOT: <https://www.datafeedwatch.com/blog/what-is-zmot>
- Kinza. (2019, March 5). *Customer experience* . Retrieved from Tech target: <https://www.techtarget.com/searchcustomerexperience/definition/digital-marketing>
- Unesco. (2023, 1 20). *Digital* . Retrieved from Digi: <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000227436>